

THE FUNCTIONING OF THE NOUN IN GERMAN LANGUAGE (CASE CATEGORY)

Azamatova Gulnoza Sunnatovna

Samarkand State University, PhD student

***Аннотация.** Цель исследования – изучить многообразие функций, которые выполняет имя существительное в современном немецком языке. Рассмотреть грамматические категории имени существительного, определить место грамматической категории падежа среди грамматических категорий имени существительного на материале современного немецкого языка. Научная новизна заключается в том, что при изучении категории падежа из падежной системы выделен родительный падеж, с одной стороны, как исчезающий, с другой – как маркер синтаксических функций имени существительного. Определена роль артикля, которому многие зарубежные и отечественные лингвисты приписывают вспомогательную функцию наряду с именем существительным, называя его сопроводителем имени существительного. В результате исследования были выявлены особенности функционирования имени существительного в немецком языке, определены функции падежей, указаны причины вытеснения родительного падежа из падежной системы немецкого языка и определяющая роль артикля в формировании смысла предложения.*

***Ключевые слова:** грамматическая категория; имя существительное; определённость падежа; неопределённость падежа; функции.*

***Abstract.** The purpose of the research is to study the variety of functions performed by a noun in the modern German language. We consider the noun grammatical categories, determine the place of the case grammatical category among the noun grammatical categories on the material of modern German language. The scientific novelty lies in the fact that, when studying the case category, the genitive case is singled out from the case system, on the one hand, as disappearing, on the other, as a marker of the syntactic functions of a noun. We define the role of the article, to which many foreign and domestic linguists attribute an auxiliary function along with a noun, calling it the accompanying noun. As a result of the study, we identify the features of a noun functioning in German language, determine the cases functions, and indicate the reasons for the displacement of the genitive case from the case system of the German language and the defining role of the article in the formation of a sentence meaning.*

***Keywords:** grammatical category; noun; case definitiveness; case indefiniteness; functions.*

INTRODUCTION. For many decades, the peculiarities of the functioning of the noun and its categories have attracted the attention of scientists. In this article, special interest is given to the category of case, which is characteristic of many languages, but it is strikingly inscribed in their systems.

The relevance of the study of nouns in the German language is due to the fact that the noun is the second most important part of speech after the verb (nouns make up more than half of the vocabulary of the German language). To date, there are many different views on the phenomena discussed in this article, including the category of case. The existence of opposite points of view proves the relevance of the study of the category of case, in addition, case semantics, morphological structure of case are of particular interest to modern linguistic science.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. Research objectives: to determine the syntactic functions of the noun in the modern German language, to analyze the role of the article as an accompanying noun, the case system of the German language, to establish the fact of displacement of the genitive case (hereinafter genitive).

The theoretical prerequisites of the research are the works of domestic and foreign scientists in the field of:

- general linguistics: E. Benveniste [1], V.V. Vinogradov [2];
- historical grammar: O. Behagel [3], L.R. Zinder, T.V. Stroeva [4], V. Schmidt [5];
- functional grammar: P. Eisenberg [6], K. Donhauser [7], K. Duden [8], P. Polenz [9], G. Rausch [10], G. Helbig, J. Bush [11], I. Fleischer, O. Schaller [12];
- Comparative Linguistics: Yu.S. Stepanov [13].

The practical value of the research lies in the fact that the material considered in this article can be used in the practice of teaching German in the courses of theoretical and practical grammar of modern German language, special courses on the problems of functional grammar; in the preparation of teaching aids, writing term papers and final qualifying papers.

A noun in German can perform various syntactic functions: the function of the subject, complement, predicate, which are primary. The main functions that a noun performs include the following: circumstances, definitions, predicate and its nominal part. In addition, the noun forms syntactic unities with prepositions, postpositions and counting words.

RESULTS. The variety of syntactic functions performed by nouns, which lead to the complication and expansion of the meaning of objectivity, is indicated by many

researchers who have been considering the functioning of nouns in the German language.

It should be noted that the noun has such grammatical categories as:

- number category;
- case category;
- category of certainty/uncertainty;
- category of the genus [14, p. 141].

DISCUSSION. Foreign researchers consider the noun as the main word in such a nominal group, and the article is attributed an auxiliary function along with the noun, calling it the accompanying noun.

An interesting look at the functioning of the article by P. Eisenberg, who notes that it is impossible to unambiguously consider the article as an auxiliary word, and the noun as the main word. Due to the fact that often a noun cannot function without an article, however, an article can also be used without a noun.

Der Baum wird gefällt. Baum wird gefällt. Der wird gefällt [6, S. 160].

The features of the manifestation of the category of certainty / uncertainty from a formal point of view are most directly related to the functioning of syntactic units: article + noun.

Ist das ein Strand oder ein Ufer? Beides. Das Ufer sagt man von Flüssen, Teichen, Meeren. Der Strand sagt man vom Ufer des Meeres und auch von der Stelle am Meer, wo man badet. If we talk about the category of certainty and uncertainty, we should pay attention to the fact that two nouns are used to designate the shore in the sentence: *das Ufer (shore)* and *der Strand (beach)* with an indefinite article, since the noun shore is mentioned in the sentence for the first time. In addition, in the sentence we observe the use of two nouns belonging to different genera, but which are synonyms and characterize the noun shore in German.

In the following sentences, both nouns are used by the author with a definite article, which shows a different gender in the nouns, which indicates the presence of a morphological feature. In this regard, it should be noted that the main syntactic function of the article is the function of the "escort" of the noun.

As a confirmation of this fact we will give an example that demonstrates that the article acts as a carrier of morphological indicators of the noun case. We are talking about the use of neuter or feminine nouns in the nominative (hereinafter nominative) and accusative cases (hereinafter accusative).

Das Mädchen besucht die Türkei. (The girl is visiting Turkey). In the presented example, there is such a phenomenon as homonymy of the means of expression of nominative and accusative for nouns. *Mädchen (girl)* and *die Türkei (Turkey)*, as they

reflect the distinctive grammatical features in this sentence. Using the word order in a sentence, this phenomenon can be eliminated, since the first place is occupied by the noun *das Mädchen* in the nominative, which performs the function of the subject. The word order eliminates homonymy: the first place is occupied by the subject in the nominative; the second is *die Türkei* –the complement in the accusative.

Let's consider case as a grammatical category that makes it easy to understand the object-subject relations between words, to show their syntactic roles, that is, to determine the meaning of the entire sentence. E.I. Shendels refers this category to morphological, defining it not by the number of syntactic functions, but by how they relate. by the number of forms that differ within one word, confined to certain grammatical meanings [15, pp. 98-99].

In this study, we share the point of view of L.R. Zinder and T.V. Stroeva on the category of case. Scientists refer the category of case to the syntactic category. The statement that the case is not any expression of the relationship between words, but only the expression of this relationship using the form of the word (the relationship between words can be expressed, for example, using a preposition), we consider justified [4, p. 75].

Und ich weiß es: Durch den Bodensee. Hier hat er nämlich keine Ufer. Richtig? Jedesmal, wenn ich am Ufer entlang gehe, denke ich daran. (And I know it: through Lake Constance. It has no shores here. Right? Every time I walk along the shore, I think about it).

Note that the German language has retained four cases, and each case has its own (basic) grammatical meaning associated with the performance of various syntactic functions. The nominative case (nominative) refers to the original case form of the noun, since nouns are used in the nominative to indicate the actor, objects, phenomena: *der Herr* (lord), *die Frau* (woman), *das Kind* (child). Nouns in the nominative act in the following functions:

- subject function: *Das Kind spielt Klavier. (Child playing piano);*
- predicative function: *Das Kind ist krank. (The child is sick);*
- when contacting: *Mensch! Was kostet es? Man! (How much does it cost?);*
- in named sentences (a characteristic feature of such sentences is the sequence of sentences).

But sometimes a series of nominations in the text is possible in the form of a number of existential, eventful and other nominative statements:

Ich folgte ihm in sein Zimmer. Eine Matratze auf dem Boden, eine Keiderstange neben dem Fenster, Bücher bis unter die Decke, eine Glasplatte auf zwei Böden des Schreibtischs, obendrauf ein PC [14, s. 160].

Obviously, in this case, the chain of nominations allows you to give a description of the space, emphasizing its characteristics and preferences of its owner: an excess of things, their disorder, emphasis on the interests of the person living in the room – reading books, working at the computer, indifference to comfort and clothes. In our opinion, the genitive case (genitive) is curious. Many Germanists explain the tendency of the disappearance of the genitive by the fact that this case is almost displaced from German dialects and is practically not used in everyday colloquial speech, partially replaced by the dative case. Some linguists indicate the primary syntactic function of the genitive – the attribute function.

V. Schmidt notes that the genitive shows the relation of one noun to another [5, S. 134]. This is the case of the adnominal definition, the attribute function is a generalized value of the genitive, which expresses the relation of a real concept to others. Supporting Bush's point of view, we believe that in modern German the genitive performs not only the function of an attribute, but also a number of other syntactic functions:

– object function to a simple verb predicate: *Sie gedachten der Toten.* (*They commemorated the dead*);

– the function of the object to the nominal predicate: *Der Wanderer ist des Weges unkundig.* (*The traveler does not know the way*);

– predicative function: *Der Patient ist frohen Mutes.* (*The patient is filled with courage*);

– adverbial definition function: *Er besuchte uns eines Abends.* (*He visited us in the evening*);

– Detection function: *Das Auto des Klinikdirektors stand vor der Universität* [3, S. 208]. (*The clinic director's car was parked in front of the university*).

The dative case (dative) performs the function of complement: *Ich gebe dem Kind das Buch.* (*I give the child a book*). If there are two additions in the sentence, then the second is used in the accusative case (accusative). As in the previous examples with a child and a book. The dative is interesting as a marker of indirect complement, as well as in combination with adjectives (with the adjectives *teuer*, *fern*, etc.).

The accusative case (accusative) performs the function of complement: *Ich gebe dem Kind das Buch* (*I give the child a book*). In this sentence, the noun *das Buch* is used in the accusative, answering the question of the accusative was? In addition, there are direct complement accusative, internal content, free and absolute accusative.

Summarizing all of the above, it is necessary to draw conclusions: a noun in the German language can perform various syntactic functions, the diversity of which is indicated by many researchers when considering the functioning of nouns in the German language.

CONCLUSIONS. The noun has such grammatical categories as the category of number, the category of case, the category of certainty / uncertainty, the category of gender. The tendency of the disappearance of the genitive is explained by the fact that this case is almost displaced from German dialects and is practically not used in everyday colloquial speech, partially replaced by the dative case.

In the light of modern grammatical theory, when considering the case, we should talk about the case system as a whole, embodying the paradigmatic and syntagmatic interrelation of all its members, that is, all individual cases of the language. This circumstance can serve as a prerequisite for further study of the case system of the German language.

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